

Environmental and food safety considerations in precision agriculture

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Abstract

Precision agriculture and Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) cover a number of activities that relate to food safety, appropriate use of chemicals and reduction of the residue level on food crops, minimal negative impacts of agricultural production on the environment, and occupational safety and welfare.

In a review current and future potential environmental and food safety contributions are discussed. Quantitative information on environmental benefits from precision agriculture technology is discussed nitrogen application, weed control and pest and disease control. Potential environmental benefits from implementation of other precision technology in combination with changing agricultural practices are listed.

In conclusion, technology development and precision agriculture will have benefits for consumers in terms of a more efficient healthy production with lower chemical inputs and reduced environmental risks.

Introduction

Good Agricultural Practices (Gap)

Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) in general cover a number of activities on the farm that relate to:

1. food safety criteria derived from the application of generic HACCP principles;
 - avoiding the inappropriate use of chemicals and reduce the level of residues found on food crops;
 - environmental protection to minimise negative impacts of agricultural production on the environment;
 - occupational health, safety and welfare criteria on farms, including socially related issues;
 - where applicable, a global level of animal welfare criteria on farms.

Precision agriculture (PA) practices can be considered as major tools towards good agricultural practices. The contribution of PA to a minimization of the environmental impact are discussed below for Nitrogen management, weed control and pest and disease management. Other potential environmental gains are also given in a summarizing table 1.

Environmental impact of precision agriculture

Nitrogen

Development of effective diagnostic systems to spatially and timely distinguish nitrogen deficiency from other causes of altered crop conditions can be a good contribution to limit the environmental impact of excessive nitrogen input. Excessive nitrogen input, at the wrong moment is not efficient for production and creates risk of degrading water quality. Diacono et al., 2013, analyzed the literature of the last 10-15 years about precision nitrogen management of wheat. Their summary included different tools and approaches like treatment maps, in season nitrogen management decisions and sensor based nitrogen rate recommendations. The main conclusions from the review can be summarized as (Diacono et al., 2013):

- sensor-based nitrogen management systems when compared with common farmer practices showed high increases in the nitrogen use efficiency of up to 368 per cent;
- these systems saved nitrogen fertilizers, from 10 per cent to about 80 per cent less nitrogen, and reduced residual nitrogen in the soil by 30–50 per cent, without either reducing yields or influencing grain quality;

- precision nitrogen management based on real-time sensing and fertilization had the highest profitability of about \$5–\$60 per hectare compared to undifferentiated applications.

The above results do not resolve the potential contradictions between maximizing the yield, optimizing the profit or nitrogen management towards minimizing the environmental impact of grain production. The environmental concern is that the incremental recovery for the last unit of nitrogen fertilizer applied (i.e., nitrogen use efficiency, NUE) near the point of maximum economic yield is <10 per cent (Scheppers, 2008). The correct timing of the split nitrogen fertilizer application should also take disease management into account. This in turn can reduce the amount of pesticides required.

The Nitrate directive of the EU states the annual amount of manure based N-fertilizer (170kg/ha/year) that can be applied. This manure also includes P and the depth of vertical placement of the manure may then be a compromise between reducing the volatilization losses of ammonia and the uptake by roots or surface runoff of P. Precision agriculture using GPS based technology for site specific balancing the P inputs and the P removed with the crop can contribute to reducing environmental effects. The application rate of manure as well as the depth of injection is the adjusted according to the local soil composition and fertilizer requirements and the manure composition (Saeys et al., 2008).

Weed control

Chemical weed control and mechanical weed control can both have many applications in precision agriculture. The environmental effects of the two approaches are different. Gerhards and Oebel (2006) concluded in a 2-year study that a map based approach to patch spraying can reduce herbicide use in winter cereals by about 6 to 81 per cent. It can be expected that combining inline weed detection with immediate herbicide spraying can lead to similar savings in herbicide use. Chemical weed control can leave residues in the soil or cause (harmful?) chemical drift. Herbicide resistant weeds have appeared forcing farmers to either use higher doses or switch to yet different molecules as herbicides.

Thermal weed control uses either steam or direct flaming to kill the weeds. In precision mechanical weed control within rows weed and crop discrimination is also used followed by near robotic weeding action. Mechanical weed control usually requires a higher level of mechanical energy and hence of fossil fuel. Thermal weed control mostly burns the above ground part of the weed, causing regrowth and perhaps more frequent treatments leading to high energy requirements. Working width of sprayers are larger than those of mechanical weeders which gives the former an advantage in terms of area covered by one operator. There have been efforts to promote the use of small field robots for automatic and unsupervised mechanical weeding or chemical weeding using micro-nozzles for herbicide delivery (Slaughter et al., 2008). It is an appealing technology but no extensive field testing on the technical reliability nor on the effectiveness in environmentally friendly weed control were published thus far.

In an evaluation of band spraying supplemented by inter-row cultivation, it was shown that spraying herbicide on only the maize rows can save up to 70 per cent of the amount of herbicides normally applied by broadcast spraying (ENDURE, 2008). One could consider that precision row spraying and row following for mechanical cultivation can even further reduce the herbicide use.

Deytieux et al. (2012) studied Integrated Weed Management (IWM) in arable crops. IWM relies on the combination of various measures for preventing, avoiding and suppressing weeds, with the aim of reducing the reliance on herbicides and their environmental impacts. Compared with a standard reference, IWM-based cropping system tested over a multi-annual experiment, were favourable for the energy demand, the global warming potential, the eutrophication and acidification, the aquatic and terrestrial eco-toxicity. However, the ranking of the cropping systems changed significantly with the two other functions (both 'production' and 'income' functions) (Deytieux et al. 2012).

Perhaps a combination of precision weed control, either mechanical or chemical with adapted cropping systems can lead to an effective Integrated Weed Management approach of the second generation that overcomes some of the farmers resistance to IWM and still achieves considerable environmental benefits. Indeed, IWM reduces overall the reliance on herbicides while precision spraying spatially reduces the use of herbicides.

Disease and Pest control

Early observation of the outbreak of a disease followed by early treatment is most likely the most economical way for disease control. This implies an early detection. One approach could be based on different spatial and temporal scales of monitoring. At those different scales information is required for correct identification or classification of diseases or of plants or crops. There remains the difficulty that sometimes the first signals of a disease can only be observed at a very small scale as discussed by Mahlein et al. (2012, 2016). Repetitive inspection of all the leaves in a field for potential infection creates a problem an extremely large dataset that should be processed in near-real time. The development of patterns in time and space, recorded by hyperspectral imaging may help to identify disease or stress influencing crops on the tissue level and on the canopy level.

Moshou et al. (2011) describe a system in which a disease map, based on automated optical sensing and intelligent prediction, provided a spatially variable recommendation for spraying that could lead to substantial savings of up to 84.5 per cent in pesticides, with financial and environmental benefits.

Sciarretta et al. (2011) report on site-specific Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies to decrease as much as possible the quantity of utilized insecticides and the total treated area, compared to uniform IPM protocols. To achieve this purpose, the strategy was to direct curative efforts towards the areas of vineyards with the highest level of oviposition, excluding areas with low egg density. Following precision targeting control, they obtained a reduction of between 80 per cent and 50 per cent of the covered surface compared to uniform IPM. These results varied between years. A major limitation is the higher sampling cost for precision IPM. However, there are indications that it may be possible to identify insects and the population density for example through optical detection of the wing beat characteristics (Van Roy et al., 2014).

Sensing the canopy structure of orchards and real time adjustment of the liquid flow can reduce the applied volume of pesticides by 22.7 per cent (Llorens et al. 2013). Oberti et al. (2016) explored selective targeting such that pesticides are deposited only where and when they are needed and at the correct dose. For powdery mildew on grape vines, they claim that the robot was able to automatically detect and spray from 85 per cent to 100 per cent of the diseased area within the canopy and to reduce the pesticide use from 65 per cent to 85 per cent when compared to a conventional homogeneous spraying of the canopy.

To avoid overdose or under-dose of a crop protection treatment the application rates of plant-protection products need to be adapted to the plant mass present when the spray is applied. Under-dose might induce pesticide resistance development. Similar observations can be made for field crops. Since the leaf area and leaf area index changes during the growing season it is advisable that an accurate model based estimation is available supported by on-the-go measurements to account for spatial variability.

Advances with the greatest environmental effects

The following PA techniques are considered to have the greatest positive environmental effects or potential:

- Use of PA technologies in combination with digital elevation maps and soil erosion measures to reduce erosion risks;
- Use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) for detection of diseases and weeds as a more flexible and versatile management support system. If suitable image treatments become available then this technology can be a good support for frequent crop monitoring and early warning of impending problems;
- In orchards and vineyards: mechanical and thermal weed control within and between rows;
- Patch spraying with herbicides in field crops, based on economic and crop yield considerations of weed infestation
- Introduction of equipment for pest and disease control in orchards that include tree architecture, tree volume and shape. In the near future this could be complimented with disease detection;
- Using less pesticides by better risk-based spatial and temporal interventions;

- Detect insects that may damage grain kernels crops which in turn can lead to fungal growth and toxin production. When the insect population is large then insecticide may be needed. Alternatively, spatially fungicide application may be required on areas where insects are active in order to reduce the incidence of mycotoxins;
- Use the relation between nitrogen-fertilizer rate, time of use, crop and environmental condition and the risk for fungal development for site specific variable rate (VR) application of fertilizers;
- Use historical data fertilizer, water and chemical protection in relation to crop yields and compare these with site specific crop growth models. Perhaps reverse modelling can help in future decisions for improved management.
- Look in more detail and apply a more versatile detection of variability and availability of phosphorus in the soils, in connection with the crop requirements;
- Use of monitoring systems for nitrogen and phosphorus in ground water and the relation with timing and rate of fertilizer application as well as weather conditions and soil maps (or soil variability). Analyze this information over time in season and over several season) to draw conclusions for better management;
- Avoid contamination through irrigation by precise placement of drip irrigation, monitoring the system such that water does not get in contact with leafy vegetables;
- Use GPS, climatic conditions and wind direction to avoid spray drift that can damage neighboring crops or make them unfit for consumption. Similar approach is needed for spreading of liquid and solid manure on fields;
- Use PA for reducing risks from microbial contamination or toxin contamination that could affect human health;
- Look at potential diverging effects of different local, national or European policies that may have adverse environmental impact when applying PA;
- Low cost environmental monitoring tools for nitrates, or other chemical is the drainage or runoff water from fields can be a stimulus as these may show the environmental effects of PA and be a basis for rewards. At this moment, the regional nitrate monitoring combined with management measures is showing its effect on drinking water quality.
- Information technology in agriculture can support and enhance the environmental impacts of precision agriculture in many different ways. Modern farm equipment relies on electronics and software for controls ('fly by wire concept') for continuously changing operations like flow rate of fertilizers or adjusting machine components. A comparison with prescribed doses is possible and these are transferred to a farm computer or even to a traceability system. In this way the environmental effects of precision agriculture can be continuously evaluated by farmers for improved future management. The data can also serve automatically to certify that a farmer is operating in the framework of environmentally friendly good agricultural practices. The farmer says what he does.

Conclusions

Precision agriculture should not only be technology (equipment) driven. Long term and alternative agronomic practices should be included to come to an economic and environmentally stable situation. This also includes operator safety and consumer safety: consumer safety in PA is affected by chemical fertilizers (like nitrate) in the drinking water, chemical residues in the edible plants that exceed MRL as well as fungal toxins that arise from crop diseases that have not been adequately dealt with in the field.

Precision agriculture tools allow an efficient and optimized crop production depending on the spatial and temporal conditions. It may also imply that farmers and managers now become aware of those sites that do not yield economic benefits and hence should not be cultivated. When these tools lead to a more efficient higher yield in some locations, then other sites or areas can be better taken out of production and returned to nature.

The benefits for society and the environmental benefits are the reduced use of potentially harmful pesticides, the reduction of fertilizer efflux to the groundwater, the reduction of soil erosion, the scope for preservation or re-establishing of vulnerable nature areas. The uptake of the technology by farmers requires encouragement from society as well as univocal supporting measures to be incorporated in the national agricultural policy.

Table 1. Expected environmental gains from main PA processes and techniques

No.	Process	Technique	Expected environmental gains
1	Timeliness of working under favourable weather conditions	Automatic machine guidance with GPS	Reduction in soil compaction Reduce carbon footprint (10 % reduced fuel consumption in field operations)
2	Leave permanent vegetation on key location and at field borders	Automatic guidance and contour cultivation on hilly terrain	Reduction of erosion (from 17 to 1 tonnes/ha/year and perhaps lower) Reduction of runoff of surface water and reduced runoff fertilizers Reduced flood risk
3	Reduce or slow down water flow between potato/vegetable ridges to slow water	- micro-dams or micro-reservoirs made between ridges("tied ridges") - ridges along field contours	Reduced sediment runoff Reduced fertilizer runoff
4	Keep fertilizer or pesticide at recommended distances from water ways	- Automatic guidance based on geographic information - Section control of sprayers and fertilizer distribution	Avoidance/elimination of direct contamination of river water
5	Avoid overlap of pesticide or fertilizer application	- Section control of sprayers and fertilizer distribution	Reduce/avoid excessive chemical input in soil and risk of water pollution
6	Variable rate manure application	On the go manure composition sensing Depth of injection adjustment	Reduced ground water pollution Reduced ammonia emissions into the air
7	Precision irrigation	Soil texture map	Avoidance of excessive water use or water logging. Reduction of fresh water use
8	Patch herbicide spraying in field crops	Weed detection (on line/weed maps)	Reduction of herbicide use with map-based approach (in winter cereals by 6–81% for herbicides against broad leaved weeds and 20–79% for grass weed herbicides*. Reduction of 15.2–17.5% in the area applied to each field was achieved with map-based automatic boom section control versus no boom section control**. 24.6% average herbicide savings was achieved in tramline spraying field trials
9	Early and localized pest or disease treatment	Disease detection - Multisensor optical detection - Airborne spores detection - Volatile sensors	Reduction of pesticide use with correct detection and good decision model (84.5% savings in pesticides possible. (Moshou et al., 2011)
10	Orchard and vineyard precision spraying	- Tree size and architecture detection - - Precision IPM	Reduction in pesticide use up to 20 – 30 % Reduction of sprayed area of 50-80%

No.	Process	Technique	Expected environmental gains
11	Variable rate nitrogen fertilizer application according to crop requirements and weather conditions	Crop vegetation index based on optical sensors Soil nutrient maps	Improvement of nitrogen use efficiency. Reduction of residual nitrogen in soils by 30 to 50 %
12	Variable rate phosphorus fertilizer application according to crop requirements and weather conditions	Crop vegetation index Soil nutrient maps	Improvement of phosphorus recovery of 25 %
13	Crop biomass estimation	Crop vegetation index	Adjust the fungicide dose according to crop biomass (Jensen and Jørgensen 2016)
14	Mycotoxin reduction	Crop vegetation index and fungal disease risk	Optimisation of fertilizer dose and fungicide use on the basis of higher disease risk in areas with high crop density

*Gerhards and Oebel 2006

**Luck et al 2010

***Dammer and Wartenberg 2007

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